

FACTORS IMPACTING WORK LIFE BALANCE FOR EMPLOYEES IN ORGANIZATIONS FROM MALAYSIA

¹Dr. Siti Aida Samikon, ²BUNENGI HENRY DAGOGO

PhD Aspirant in Limkokwing University of Creative Technology. PhD in Management

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7188607>

Published Date: 12-October-2022

Abstract: Work–life balance is the term used to describe the balance that an individual needs between time allocated for work and other aspects of life, which is the ability to manage balance between work and personal life. Still there are some factors which affects work-life balance of employees in organizations. The present paper aims at identifying the factors in work life influencing work-life balance of employees in organizations. The present study would be beneficial for organizations in designing work-life policies and programmes for employees.

Keywords: Work–life balance, employees in organizations.

1. INTRODUCTION

Work Life Balance (WLB) plays important role in employee's performance. In order to get competitive advantages, the talented, qualified and satisfied employees are needed to the organizations. Nowadays work-life balance system is being practiced to motivate their employees.

Currently, there are quite a large number of studies that have been done looking into the issue of work-life balance. Some of these studies examine factors that lead to the uptake of work-life programmes implemented by organizations while others studied the factors affecting work-life balance. More importantly, all these studies focused on how factors could improve the work-life balance of today's workforce, and all of them agreed that there are many factors that could influence it. The research needs to be conducted to discover other factors that could contribute to work-life balance. Hence, it is the objective of this study to fill this gap, and determine the relationship between several individual factors and organizational factors to work-life balance.

For many individuals in Malaysia—women and men alike—work life balance has become the proverbial “brass ring” for which they strive in their efforts to balance family, work, and personal interests. Nevertheless, work life balance is not simply essential for the health and well-being of individuals, but is also cost-efficient and stability-enhancing for institutions and work-environments (Perrons, 2013).

Greenhaus et al. (2014) found that equal investment of time involvement in work and family would increase the quality of work life. To exhibit positive time balance, an individual should commit a considerable amount of time to their combined work and family and to be able to distribute this time equally. Success on balancing work and social roles becomes a strong contributor to an individual's mood. Work life balance was found to predict well-being and the overall quality of life (Gropel and Kuhl, 2014). In this study, we examined the factors affect work life balance for employee in Malaysia.

1.1 Problem Statement

A study of work life balance is a paramount importance, the nature being different for each category of employees depending upon their needs. A good quality of work life reduces absenteeism, accidents & attrition, which is useful to improve production, organizational effectiveness, morale of an employee and economic development of the country. So an attempt has been made to know about the employees satisfaction on WLB and its influence on their working and social environment.

Work-life balance practices normally refer to an organization offering one of the following — flexible work options, organizational support for dependent care, and personal or family leave (McDonald, Brown, & Bradley, 2012; Thornthwaite, 2014). These practices are becoming more important due to technological advances that have blurred the boundaries between work and non-work domains, the increasing number of dual-earner families and single-parents, as well as longer working hours, giving rise to work-home interference. Research on the negative effects of work-home interference on both employees and organizations has been well-documented (Beauregard, 2014). According to the business case, by offering these practices, organizations not only attract new employees but are also able to reduce work-life conflict among existing ones; hence increasing organizational performance by providing more control to employees to manage their work and family demands (Beauregard & Henry, 2011; Kossek & Friede, 2013).

Malaysia is a multi-ethnic, multi-religious country with three main ethnic groups; Malay (50.4% of the population), Chinese (23.7%), and Indian (7.1%). The rest is made up of indigenous peoples (11%, mostly in East Malaysia) and other races (7.8%, CIA: The World Factbook, 2012). The New Economic Policy instituted the following year after the riots in 1969, had two objectives, elimination of poverty and social restructuring. Though the policy was supposed to be racially blind, in reality, it had and continues to be one of giving preferential treatment to Malays.

The Employment Act (EA) is the main legislation covering the relationship between employer and employee, and specifies the minimum standards with respect to wages, work hours, leave, termination and lay-off benefits. The Act covers those earning RM2000 or less (amendment 2012) and those engaged in manual labour. It also includes individuals responsible for supervising those engaged in 'manual work,' regardless of their salary level.

Work Hours — Under the Act, a maximum of 48-hours a week is permissible, with daily working hours not exceeding eight. These eight hours of work must be performed within ten continuous hours from the time work begins for the day. Work performed after the completed ten-hour period is deemed overtime work even though an employee may not have actually done eight hours of work in a day. Rest or break times are excluded in calculating the work hours.

Burnout — Almost 64% of employees do less than 150 minutes of physical activity a week, the highest percentage compared to Singapore, Hong Kong and Australia. Most employees are sedentary throughout most of their working hours. We sit down on our butts for way too long! 90% of Malaysians do not eat a balanced diet, which has led to 12.5% of Malaysian employees being obese. 29% of Malaysian employees are at risk of having one or more chronic conditions, such as a heart or kidney condition, cancer, diabetes, or high blood pressure.

Minimum Wage — In the latest amendment to the Act, a minimum wage of RM1050, has been introduced in Peninsula Malaysia (RM800 for employees in Sabah and Sarawak)

Work life balance has been studied within the context of business, for-profit organizations (Blair-Loy, 2013; English, 2013; Stephens, 2013). It has also been explored within higher education organizations (Johnsrud & Rosser, 2012). Work life balance is even a weekly column in The Chronicle of Higher Education. Within higher education, many distinct subpopulations might be explored through a work life balance lens: from adult students to tenured faculty members, student affairs professionals to student athletes.

In terms of work life balance, Quality Work Life (QWL) has been a cause of concern in recent years. This has captured the attention of employees and employers, more so due to workplaces competing for suitably qualified and competent employees. Employers have utilized WLB factors as a tool for attracting and retaining talented employees. Higher education institutions have not been an exception to this growing phenomena. Organizations need to seek ways of improving their employees WLB through healthy and safe working conditions; better conditions of service; and adequate and fair compensation amongst other factors.

1.2 Objectives of Study

Main Objective of Study :

To investigate whether quality of work life, job satisfaction & employee commitment will impact work life balance irrespective of the demographical characteristics of employees like age, gender, marital status and work experience levels.

Research Sub-objective:

- 1) To determine whether quality work life impact WLB
- 2) To determine whether job satisfaction impact WLB
- 3) To determine whether employee commitment impact WLB

1.3 Significance of Study

Many companies find that paying attention to the needs of employees can benefit the company in terms of productivity, employee loyalty and company reputation. Work life balance is important because of the following reasons:

1. Safe and healthy working conditions

Employers are increasingly trying to provide better working conditions to their workers as compared to their competitors. Flexi-hours of work, zero risk physical conditions of work and safety against noise, pollution, fume, gases etc. go a long way in effecting the quality of work life.

2. Increase productivity

Programmes which help employees balance their work and lives outside the work can improve productivity. A company's recognition and support

— through its stated values and policies — of employees' commitments, interests and pressures, can relieve employees' external stress.

This allows them to focus on their jobs during the workday and helps to minimize absenteeism. The result can be both enhanced productivity and strengthened employee commitment and loyalty.

3. Social integration in work organization

An employee develops a sense of belongingness to the organization where he works. Discrimination among the employees on the basis of age, gender, cast, creed, religion etc. can act as a hindrance in the way of social integration. Workers develop self-respect as a result of social integration and improves the quality of work life.

4. Improve the quality of working lives

Minimizing work-life role conflict helps prevent role overload and people have a more satisfying working life, fulfilling their potential both in paid work and outside it.

Work life balance can minimize stress and fatigue at work, enabling people to have safer and healthier working lives. Workplace stress and fatigue can contribute to injuries at work and home. Self-employed people control their own work time to some extent. Most existing information on work-life balance is targeted at those in employment relationships. However, the self-employed too may benefit from maintaining healthy work habits and developing strategies to manage work flows which enable them to balance one with other roles in their lives.

1.4 Definitions of Key Terms

This section provides definitions for key terms and acronyms used in this study. Some terms are used interchangeably throughout the dissertation, and these are also noted here.

Work Life Balance (WLB): the degree to which an individual is able to simultaneously balance the temporal, emotional, and behavioral demands of both paid work and family responsibilities (Hill et al., 2012).

Job Satisfaction: directly linked to an individual's happiness, and there is a positive relationship between the strength of an individual's identification and involvement in a particular relationship between job and life satisfaction (Kornhauser, 2011).

Quality Work Life (QWL): A relatively new concept which is defined as the overall quality of an individual's working life. QWL is sometimes considered as a sub-concept of the broad concept of quality of life, which refers to the overall quality of an individual's life.

Employee Commitment: The strength of an individual's identification and involvement in a particular organization.

2. BACKGROUND OF STUDY

This chapter will focus on finding literature on past research for factors, to review the factors in work life balance for an organization, the work life for the employee in the organization is based on the experience of the work. In addition, this chapter will also investigate and examine the factors in work life balance for employees in organization.

2.1 Employee and work life balance

There is a need for employees to maintain work-life balance, otherwise both performance at work and everywhere else will be threatened. However, maintaining work-life balance is not easy, especially if the individual (i.e. employees) do not have the capacity to do it effectively and the organization that they work for do nothing to help them. Hence, there is a need to determine factors that could help employees maintain their work-life balance. Previous studies have shown that there are many factors that could affect work-life balance. Some of the factors have shown to have a positive relationship with work-life balance. These factors include job satisfaction (Saif, Malik, & Awan, 2010); and telework (Felstead, Jewson, Phizaklea, & Walters, 2002; Morganson, Major, Oborn, Verine, & Heelan, 2010; Hilbrecht, Shaw, Johnson, & Andrey, 2008). Finding a factor of work life balance is in spite of the foregoing and the seemingly extensive devotion to the philosophy of work-life balance, studies such as Bond (2009) Hochschild (2007) and Okeke (2011) show that the mere availability of far-reaching and liberal work-life balance policies does not necessarily result in prevalent employment by workers or subsequent advances in work-life balance and reductions in work-life conflict. According to De Bruin and Dupuis (2010) creating work-life balance programmes is one thing, getting employees to make use of them is a totally different matter. There is considerable contention about the effectiveness of organizational work-life balance policies in delivering flexibility and reducing stress and job dissatisfaction modern workplace.

2.1.1 Work-Life Balance

Work-life balance has to do with proper prioritizing between work career, ambition, lifestyle, health, pleasure, family and spiritual development. The concept of work-life balance is based on the idea that paid work and private life should be seen less as opposite priorities and more as corresponding essentials of a full life. According to Lewis (2008) the way to achieve this is to adopt a system that is conceptualized as a two-way process, which considers the needs of the workers as well as those of employers. In order to take on employers in this procedure it is imperative to show the benefits that can be obtained from employment policies and practices that sustain work-life balance, and the scope that subsists for extenuating their negative effects on the management of the business. Clark (2009) defines work-life balance as contentment and good functioning at work and at home with negligible role conflicts. Work-life balance is about finding the right balance between one's work and one's life (outside work) and about feeling comfortable with both work and non-work commitments. Many people find it difficult to manage their time in a way that is healthy for work and for personal life not because they are poor at time management, but because a good part of the time is not theirs. However, work-life balance is tricky to individually accomplish without organizational encouragement. Bird (2010) asserts that, work-life balance does not mean an equal balance adding that one's best individual work-life balance would vary over time. The right balance for one person today will without reservations be different for the same person tomorrow. The best work-life balance is different for everyone because we all have different priorities and diverse lives. However, at the centre of an effective work-life balance definition are two significant everyday concepts that are pertinent to everyone namely achievement and enjoyment.

2.2 Work-Life Benefit

The acknowledgement of achievement by senior staff members and is motivational factor to employees as it help build on the self-esteem. As far as possible, management should provide responsibilities that match the individual interest in and outside the work place. Responsibility is the opportunity to exercise authority and power through providing leadership skills, making decision and providing direction that will ensure you retain a team that is highly motivated. Some of the example include; the management giving praise, letters of commendations and end of year awards amongst others such as family trips and leisure activities in various fields. These job aspects provide employees with positive and satisfying pleasure for work and non-work activities. Communication with employees on work issues may affect work life balance (Winkler, 2010). Work-life balance is not merely defined by time divided between work-life and non-work-life. It needs to be achieved by minimizing the conflict among these two domains by balancing the multiple roles and tasks (kumarasamy, Pangil, and Isa, 2015). In other words, a person who experiences lower work-family conflict can be concluded as having achieved work-

life balance. Aside from that, there is a prior study outlined the elements in work-life balance. According to Winkler 2010, working conditions such as flexible working hours, conducive work place layout, working facilities and job equipment may affect work life balance.

Company policies governing work life benefits should be fair, realistic and humane in motivating the employees in their jobs.

2.2.1 Relationship between workplace factor and work-life balance

The study had been done by Russo et al. (2015) suggested that social support in work and non-work increase work-life balance by regulating the multiple roles of employees. Furthermore, the supervisor shows support in term of decentralizing decision-making to make employees feel comfortable with the working environment (Mas-Machuca, Berbegal-Mirabent, and Alegre, 2016). There are studies mentioned that supervisor support does not significantly increase the satisfaction towards the person's life. Wu, Rusyidi, Claiborne and McCarthy (2013) stated that the supervisor support is not significantly influencing work-life balance but pleasant working environment plays a significant role in enhancing work-life balance. In short, the researcher concluded that support from supervisor are not important if the organization provides a family friendly environment in promoting work-life balance. Work-life balance includes roles and responsibilities in work and non-work domain. The multiple roles of employees in this fast pace environment arouse the needs of work-life balance. Many organizations in societies recognize the importance of work-family culture and adopt work-life balance policies such as flexible working schedules to increase the satisfaction of employees (Sivatte, Gordon, Rojo, and Olmos, 2015).

2.3 Theoretical Framework

The dependent variable of the research is the work-life balance in an organization and independent variables to be investigated include quality work life, job satisfaction and employee's commitment.

2.4 Hypotheses

The following will be the hypotheses for the study:

- H1- Quality of work life has an impact on work life balance
- H2- Job satisfaction has a strong impact on work life balance
- H3- Employee commitment has an impact on work life balance

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter will consider the methodology or approach used. The methodology focuses on developing a questionnaire to collect demographic data as well as data relating to the variables in the study. The unit of analysis will be defined and the sample size will be determined based on past similar studies. This research will be using the statistical testing to test the hypotheses and to determine which demographic data best mediates work life balance.

3.1 Methods of study

This method will be using a questionnaire to collect data that will ultimately be used to test the hypotheses in this study. While some researchers have proposed survey instrument for the assessment of the quality of experiences, some limitation exist (Tam, 2006, 2007, Webber et al., 2013).

3.2 Type of Research

This type of research will carry out both descriptive and quantitation studies. Section A of the questionnaire will capture the demographic and descriptive aspects of the variables through likert scale questions. That seeks to ascertain the factors in work life affect work life balance for employees in organization. The sample size used will be 200 respondents and 150 responses are expected (Citation, year). Cite somebody who has used this sample size before.

3.3 Type of Data

The data will be collected via a questionnaire and there is no interview in the research design method, it will also be using the statistical package social sciences (SPSS). It will be applied to check the value and the variable, the statistical package social science will be use to analysis the work life balance for employees in the organization. In the meantime, normality test will be used to identify the skewness of the data. Every parametric test has its assumptions and normality of data is one them (Pallant, 2016)

3.3.1 Secondary Data

This data refers to data, which is collected by someone other than the user. In secondary data analysis individuals who were not involved in the collection of the data analyse the data. Secondary data maybe based on the published data or it may be based on the original data. Common source of secondary data for social science include censuses, information collected by government department, organizational records and data that was originally collected for other research purposes. Secondary data analysis offers methodological benefits and can contribute to LIS research through generating new knowledge (Heaton, 2008, Johnston, 2012; smith, 2008) Thi

3.3.2 Primary Data

The data observed or collected directly from first-hand experience. Published data and the data collected in the past or other parties is called secondary data. Primary data are data that are collected for the specific research problem at hand, using procedures that fit the research problem best. On every occasion that primary data are collected, new data are added to the existing store of social knowledge.

3.4 Population of the study

The target population for this study consists of employee Malaysia, the research will be in Malaysia this study will be looking at 100 populations, based on the factors in work life balance for employees in an organization.

3.5 Methods of Collecting Data

This sampling technique will be used in this research. This is a sample technique, which is certainly not a non-probability sampling method where subjects are selected because of their convenient accessibility and more likely the availability to the researcher. This technique is sensible since it will ensure that all participants of the populace get an indistinguishable right to share in the research sampling. Data gathering tools will be utilized to gather representations being considered.

3.6 Data Collection

The research data handled in this research are produced with the questionnaires issued. The statistical analysis adopted was a correlation, the statistical instrument is use to determine the present statistical significant affiliation concerning the dependent and independent variables. According to Kothari (2004). Correlation analysis is the relationship between two properties or the amount of measuring the extent to which the interdependence of the variable quantities.

4. FINDINGS

This section presents the analysis of the data that was collected from the respondents. Table 1 has shown the personal factors of the employees in textile industry.

Table No. 2 Demographic of Respondents

Personal factors		No of respondents	Percentage
Age	20-30 years	9	18
	30-40 years	17	34
	Above 40 years	24	48
	Total	50	100
Gender	Male	39	78
	Female	11	22
	Total	50	100
Marital status	Married	40	80
	Unmarried	10	20
	Total	50	100
Educational qualification	Illiterate	15	30
	School level	21	42
	Diploma	7	14
	Degree/Graduation	7	14
	Total	50	100
Experience	Less than 3 years	7	14
	3-5 years	13	26
	5-8 years	19	38
	Above 8 years	11	22
	Total	50	100
Salary p.m.	Below Rs.5,000	16	32
	Rs.5,000-Rs.7,000	23	46
	Above Rs.7,000	11	22
	Total	50	100
Adequate income	Yes	35	70
	No	15	30
	Total	50	100

From this table, we can observe clearly that 48% of the respondents belong to above 40 years of age group, 18% belong to 20-30 years and 34% belong to 30-40 years age group. 78% of the respondents were male and 22% were female. 80% of the respondents were married and 20% were unmarried. 30% of the respondents were illiterate, 42% have studied up to school level and the same numbers of respondents have completed their graduations and diploma education. 38% of the respondents have had 5-8 years of experience and 14% have less than 3 years of experience, 46% of the respondents monthly salary being Rs.5,000-Rs.7,000 and 22% earned above Rs.7,000. 70% of the respondents get adequate income and 15% of the respondents do not get adequate income.

4.1 Factors impacting work life balance

Work is an integral part of our life, as it is our livelihood or career or business. On an average we spend around twelve hours daily in the work place that is one third of our entire life. Even if it is a small step towards our lifetime goal, at the end of the day it gives satisfaction and eagerness to look forward to the next day. Factors influence the quality of work life of employees has been shown in Table no.2.

Table No.2 Factor impacting work life balance

Factors	Total score	Mean	Rank
Quality of work	120	2.40	2
Job satisfaction	150	3.00	1
Employee commitment	113	2.26	3

4.2 Satisfaction On Present Level Of Quality Of Work Life

Respondents' opinion about the present level of quality of work life provided by their organization has been depicted in Table 3. Using Likert's scaling technique favorableness of the factors has been assessed.

Table No.3 Satisfaction on present level of quality of work life

Particulars	H.S	S	N	D.S	H.D.S	Likert's points	Favorability
Job Satisfaction:							
Working hours	12	21	10	5	2	3.72	F
Job freedom/rotation	7	15	11	7	10	3.04	F
Promotion, training and recognition	21	9	12	7	1	3.84	F
Compensation	6	10	14	12	8	2.88	UF
Safety and healthy working conditions:							
No risk of illness	9	16	8	10	7	3.20	F
Humanized	6	16	18	7	3	3.30	F
Quite Tolerable	29	11	5	4	1	4.26	F
Emphasis on individual	9	20	11	6	4	3.48	F
Opportunities to develop human capacities:							
Accurate information	24	17	5	3	1	4.2	F
Ideas appreciated	8	13	15	7	7	3.16	F
Technical planning	4	5	17	14	10	2.58	UF
Information of other departments	6	19	14	9	2	3.36	F
Opportunities for continued growth and security:							
Comprehensive work	13	11	17	3	6	3.44	F
Challenging work	7	9	11	15	8	3.00	F
Opportunities to Improve job	6	16	19	7	2	3.34	F
Use of newly acquired Knowledge.	6	11	13	12	8	2.90	UF

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (123-133), Month: September - December 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

To ascertain the favorableness or unfavorableness of the employees, the Likert’s scaling technique has been used.

The factors Job satisfaction, Financial needs are met and Like to continue the job have assessed as favorable factors as the calculated values are more than the normal mean value 3. Compensation has been identified as unfavorable factor whose mean value (2.88) is less than the normal mean value 3.

While analyzing the safety and healthy working conditions, all the four factors viz., no risk of illness, humanized, quite tolerable and emphasis on individual have scored as favorable factors as their mean value is higher than the normal mean value 3.

In case of opportunities to develop human capacities except technical planning other factors viz., accurate information, ideas appreciated and information of other departments have gained favorable responses from the employees. Mean value has been higher than the normal mean value.

While taking the opportunities for continued growth and security comprehensive work, challenging work and opportunities to improve the job have been scored as the favorable factors (calculated values are more than the normal mean value 3. Use of newly acquired knowledge alone has scored as unfavorable factor by the respondents (mean value is less than 3 -2.90).

4.3 Employees commitment

Employees have some expectation from the work place to improve the quality of work life. Work related requirements have direct relation with the personal affairs of the employees.

The expectations of the employees have been depicted in table no.4

Table No.4 Expectation of the employee

Expectations	No. of employees	Percentage
Higher compensation	20	40
Innovative practices to improve technical knowledge	12	24
Individual recognition	8	16
Equitable rewards	10	20

40% of the employees have expected higher compensation, 24% of the respondents have viewed that to improve their technical knowledge innovative practices to be adopted in their organization. 16% of the respondents have needed individual recognition to differentiate their work with others. Remaining 20% of them have expected equitable rewards to increase the morale and productivity of employees.

When an employee have positive perception of the quality of work life in the company, he would further probably strive to further improve the working conditions, increase production and can give quality products.

Table no.5 has shown the influence of quality of work life on employees’ performance.

Influence	No. of employees	Percentage
Improves morale	18	36
Improved productivity	20	40
Increase the level of commitment	10	20

40% of the respondents have stated that due to QWL their productivity has been increased. 36% of employee respondents have said that their morale has been improved and 20% of the respondents’ level of commitment to their work and organization has been increased because of the organizations’ quality of work life.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This is the summary of the factor impacting work life balance for employees in organizations from Malaysia, the survey result was presented in the last chapter. In this chapter, the justifications of the survey result are presented based on the comparison to existing literature. In addition, the implication, limitation and future study perspectives are discussed in this chapter.

5.1 Finding

The purpose of this study was to learn about the factors impacting work life balance for employees in organizations from Malaysia. The survey reveals that the majority of respondents are favorable in this research and some are unfavorable in the research, but the ones that are favorable is greater than the ones that are unfavorable.

Another finding of the study reveals that the mean in factors of impacting work life balance shows that employees commitment is in a higher rank of 3, quality of work is in rank 2 and job satisfaction is ranked 1 in table no: 2. 40% of the employees have expected higher compensation in the employees commitment in table no: 4.

5.2 Recommendation for Future Study

Although this research provided considerable results, several recommendations are proposed for the future studies in the similar areas of knowledge. In this research, the organization in Malaysia respondents were considered solely. The future studies can fulfill this particular area of knowledge. In addition, the existing literature review for this research limits the predictor of performance to four factors solely. The future study can be conducted to delimit several other factor such as satisfaction, attitude etc., for much precise and comparative outcomes.

5.3 Implication of the Findings

The findings of this study will contribute directly to the Malaysian organization sector. For the organization point, the result of the study will increase the knowledge on the factors impacting work life balance for employees in an organization in Malaysia. For the higher organization, findings of the study will help organizations to have a better way to evaluate their work life balance and know the areas needed to be concern in other to improve the organization.

5.4 Research Limitations

There are limitations in this research work, in this sense that not all perspectives were considered here as influence of the work life balance, hence future improvement can include that in the research. This research work is also for the most part limited on local and international organizations in Malaysia, and the future improvement ought to consolidate other industrial segment in the research.

5.5 Conclusion

As the experience of workers has a great impact on their organizations, according to the factors impacting work life balance for employees in an organization in Malaysia and employee have positive perception on the quality of work life balance in their organizations. So it is necessary to think and plan to improve the organization more, according to researchers, the study experience for people is learning and learning, and can take several steps in this area. It is also recommended that organization should have an individual recognition so as to help individual to work held in their field.

REFERENCES

- [1] Andrew.D.and Marc W. (1980). "Organisational Behaviour and Performance", Scott Foresman and company, Glenview, Illinois, 219-220C
- [2] Clutterbuck,D. (2003). "Managing the work-life Balance ", UK:Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development.8-9.
- [3] Morris,M.L and Madsen,S.R. (2007). "Advancing work-life Integration in individuals,organizations and communities", Advances in Developing HumanResources.9 (2) .439-454.
- [4] Moore,F (2007). "Work-life Balance: Contrasting Managers and workers in anMNC", Employee Relations.29 (4) 385-399.
- [5] John O. (2004). "Personal Characteristics as Predictors of Job satisfaction: Anexploratory study of IT managers in a Developing Economy", Information Technology and people.17 (3) .327-338.
- [6] Radha,V&Ashu ,K" Literature Review on the Quality of work life and their dimensions" ISOR Journal of Humanities & Social Sciences (IOSR JHSS), 4 (9) :71:80.

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (123-133), Month: September - December 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [7] Dr.Sorav & Prof. G “Sustainable quality of work life and job satisfaction” Journal of Economic Development environment and people, 2 (4) : 25-29.
- [8] Chins (1979), “Using the Social Science,” Routledge and Kegan Paul, London. 7Davis, L.E. and Trist, E. (1979), Improving the Quality of Working Life: Socio- technical Case Studies, In L.E. Davies and J.C. Taylor (Eds.), Design of Jobs, Goodyear Publishing Co, California.
- [9] Frederick, W.. (1974), The Principles of Scientific Management, in Scientific Management, Harper and Row, New York, pp. 24-25.
- [10] Harrison T.M. (1985), “Communication and Participative Decision Making: An Exploratory Study; Personnel Psychology, 3(1), 97-116.
- [11] Walton, E. (1973), Quality of Work Life: What is it? Sloan Management Review, Vol. 15 (1), 11-21. 2 Jenkins, D. (1981), QWL: Current Trends and Direction, A series of occasional paper No.3, Ontario: Quality of Work Life Centre.
- [12] Nadler, D.A., and Lawler, E.E. (1983), Quality of work life: Perceptions and Direction, Organizational Dynamics, 11(3), . 20-30.
- [13] .Florence ,M& Peter k “Quality of work, life, personality, Job satisfaction, competence, and job performance a critical review of literature” ,European Scientific journal , 11 (26) :223-226.
- [14] Preethi ,V& Dr.D.“An empirical study on relationship among quality of work life and its factors” IOSR-JBM journal of business management , 2013,12 (3) :20-28.
- [15] C.P Garg et al “Quality of work life an overview”, International journal of physical and social science, 2012 ,2 (3) .231-242.
- [16] Havolovic, S.J. (1991), —Quality of Work Life and Human Resource Outcomes Industrial Relations, Vol.30, No.3, pp.469-479
- [17] Katzell, R.A., Yankelovich, D., Fein M., Ornate, D.A. & Nash, A. (1975), —Work Productivity and Job Satisfaction, The Psychological Corporation, New York.
- [18] Dr.Sorav sadri & Prof.Conrad Goves “Sustainable quality of work life and job satisfaction” Journal of Economic Development environment and people, 2013,2 (4) 25-29.
- [19] Dundas, K. (2008). Work life balance: There is no 'one-size fits all' solution. *Managing Matters*, 7-8.
- [20] Goh, Z., Ilies, R., & Wilson, K. S. (2015). Supportive supervisors improve employees' daily lives: The role supervisors play in the impact of daily workload on life satisfaction via work–family conflict. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 89, 65-73.
- [21] Greenhaus, J. C. (2003). The relation between work-family balance and quality of life. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 510-31.
- [22] Scholarios, D. &. (2004). Work-life balance and the software worker. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 54-74.
- [23] Guest, D. (2002). Perspectives on the study of work life balance. *Social Science Information*, 255.